

Supporting Information File S3

Mathematica code for: Remodeling and the Evolution of Sexual Autonomy by Mate Choice

Samuel S. Snow^{1,2*} and Richard O. Prum²

*Corresponding author: samuel.s.snow@gmail.com

¹Université Toulouse 1 Capitole and Institute for Advanced Studies in Toulouse (IAST), Toulouse, France

²Department of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, Yale University, New Haven, Connecticut, 06511

Two-preference version of the three-locus population-genetic Remodeling model. In this version, we explore a case where R2 females prefer B2 males, but rather than mate randomly, R1 females have an equally strong preference for B1 males. We start the population at $r_2=0.5$ and $b_2=0.5$ so we can examine the effect of the protectiveness of the B2 trait, γ , in favoring one kind of female preference over another. This code explores the "invasion" of the R2 allele via analysis of the model recursion equations.

See Table 1 for definitions of alleles and key parameters.

*Note on parametrization: in the main text and Appendices S1–S3, we refer to the mutation parameter as " u " to avoid confusion with the subscript m used to denote male genotype frequencies. In the code below, the mutation parameter is denoted " m " and has been left as such to avoid the introduction of errors.

```
ClearAll[st, sb, at, c,  $\gamma$ , m, init, T1B1R1, T2B1R1, T1B2R1, T2B2R1, T1B1R2, T2B1R2,
T1B2R2, T2B2R2, genotypes, msel, fsel, r, Output, u, ab, z1, z2, zb, T2, B2,
R2, DTB, DTR, DBR, DTBR, altered, Mating, s, mgenotypes, T21, B21, R21, DTB1,
```

DTR1, DBR1, DTBR1, $\Delta T2$, $\Delta B2$, $\Delta R2$, ΔDTB , ΔDTR , ΔDBR , $\Delta DTBR$, perturb, sr, zb0, materec, Rectable, MaskProb, ZygoteGenotypes, prob, zyg1, zyg2, zygoteProb];

(*three-locus popgen simulation of
Remodeling without direct costs to coercive mating*)

(*this version uses a probabilistic formulation for how females visit and mate at male territories. Females may either visit territories randomly or choose territories based on the kind of remodeling trait (bower) they see. Once there, the male may either coerce them into mating there without the opportunity to evaluate their display, or the female may choose the mate with that male (given that he has not already coerced her) by some factor related to his attractiveness.*)

(*There is a locus for male display trait $T2/T1$, remodeling trait (protective bower) $B2/B1$, and female preference for the type of Remodeling trait (bower), $R2/R1$. We make two underlying assumptions in this model: 1) that all males will coerce if they have the opportunity, and 2) that all females have a preference for attractive $T2$ males*)

(*parameters:

(1-st) is the fraction by which males having the $T2$ allele survive relative to Males having the $T1$ allele. (1-sb) is the fraction by which males having the $B2$ allele survive relative to Males having the $B1$ allele.

(1-sr) is the fraction by which females having the $R2$ allele survive relative to females having the $R1$ allele.

(at+1) is the factor by which attractive $T2$ allele males have a relative advantage in mating success over $T1$ males.

**In this version of the model, (ab+1) is the factor by which females with the $R2$ allele prefer to visit $B2$ bowers, AND ALSO the factor by which $R1$ females prefer $B1$ bowers, so there is an equally strong preference for either. The only difference will be γ affecting the $B2$ males.

c is a number between 0 and 1 representing the rate of successful forced fertilization of a female, (or the likelihood of coercive attack) by a male without a protective bower ($B2$).

γ is a number between 0 and 1 representing the effectiveness of protective bowers at reducing a male's ability to coerce. If $\gamma=0$, then there is no effect, and if $\gamma=1$, then $B2$ males are unable to coerce, and females are free to choose the male based on his attractiveness once they are at his territory.

Lastly, we make an assumption of biased mutation at the T locus. This is meant as a proxy for a quantitative, multialleleic trait or some other process by which variation is maintained at the T locus, so that sexual selection is ongoing and we can explore the effects of sexual conflict over indirect effects in a simple population-genetic framework*)

(*the equilibrium conditions for a non-zero T2 in the absence of B and R are: $0 < st < 1$ and $0 < m < 1$ and $-1 + \frac{1+m}{(-1+m)(-1+st)} < c < \frac{at-2m-atm+st+atm+st}{at+2m+atm+st-mst}$. See Appendix S2 and Supporting Information File S2 for derivation*)

(*use these conditions to determine appropriate parameter values*)

Manipulate $\left[\left\{ -1 + \frac{1+m}{(-1+m)(-1+st)}, \frac{at-2m-atm+(1+at)(-1+m)st}{at+2m+atm+st-mst} \right\}, \left\{ \{m, 0.1\}, 0, 1 \}, \left\{ \{st, 0.1\}, 0, 1 \}, \left\{ \{at, 4\}, -1 + \frac{1+m}{(-1+m)(-1+st)}, 30 \right\} \right];$

(*set parameters*)

```
st = 1 / 10;
```

```
sb = 0;
```

```
sr = 0;
```

(*recombination and mutation rate*)

```
rtb = 1 / 2;
```

```
rbr = 1 / 2;
```

```
m = 1 / 10;
```

(*The initial frequency for T2 is the equilibrium value for when B2 and R2 equal zero. This is where female preference for T2, mutation bias, and male coercion are in balance;

See Appendix S2 and Supporting Information File S2 for derivation.*)

$$T_{eq} = \frac{1 - m + \frac{2(1+c+atc)m}{st+cst+at(-1+c+st)}}{1+m};$$

```
init = Solve[{T1B1R1 + T2B1R1 + T1B2R1 + T2B2R1 + T1B1R2 + T2B1R2 + T1B2R2 + T2B2R2 == 1,
  T2 == T2B1R1 + T2B2R1 + T2B1R2 + T2B2R2, B2 == T1B2R1 + T2B2R1 + T1B2R2 + T2B2R2,
  R2 == T1B1R2 + T2B1R2 + T1B2R2 + T2B2R2, DTB == (T2B2R1 + T2B2R2) - T2 * B2,
  DTR == (T2B1R2 + T2B2R2) - T2 * R2, DBR == (T1B2R2 + T2B2R2) - B2 * R2,
  DTBR == T2B2R2 - T2 * ((T1B2R2 + T2B2R2) - B2 * R2) -
  B2 * ((T2B1R2 + T2B2R2) - T2 * R2) - R2 * ((T2B2R1 + T2B2R2) - T2 * B2) - T2 * B2 * R2},
  {T1B1R1, T2B1R1, T1B2R1, T2B2R1, T1B1R2, T2B1R2, T1B2R2, T2B2R2}];
```

```
T1B1R1 = T1B1R1 /. init;
T2B1R1 = T2B1R1 /. init;
T1B2R1 = T1B2R1 /. init;
T2B2R1 = T2B2R1 /. init;
T1B1R2 = T1B1R2 /. init;
T2B1R2 = T2B1R2 /. init;
T1B2R2 = T1B2R2 /. init;
T2B2R2 = T2B2R2 /. init;
```

```
(*genotypes vector with initial allele frequencies and linkages*)
genotypes = Flatten[{T1B1R1, T2B1R1, T1B2R1, T2B2R1,
  T1B1R2, T2B1R2, T1B2R2, T2B2R2, T2, B2, R2, DTB, DTR, DBR, DTBR}];
```

```
(*set up the table of recombination probabilities that will yield the
distribution of zygote genotypes resulting from each mated pairing*)
```

```
Nloci = 3;
Geno = 2^Nloci;
masklim = 2^(Nloci - 1);
recreate[1] = rtb;
recreate[2] = rbr;
```

```
(*Maskprob gives the probability for a particular pattern of
recombination (a mask), based on given values of recombination
rates between different loci ("recreate" vector above)*)
```

```
MaskProb = Function[{mask, Nloci},
  For[prob = 1; z = 1, z < Nloci, z++,
    If[BitGet[mask, z] == BitGet[mask, z - 1],
      prob *= (1 - recreate[z]),
      prob *= recreate[z]]];
```

```
(*generates the two zygote genotypes (zyg1 and zyg2)
```

```

from two parental genotypes (i and j) for a given mask.*)

ZygoteGenotypes = Function[{i, j, mask},
  For[zyg1 = 0; zyg2 = 0; k = 0, k < Nloci, k++,
    If[BitGet[mask, k] == 0,
      zyg1 = BitOr[zyg1, (BitAnd[i, (2^k)])];
      zyg2 = BitOr[zyg2, (BitAnd[j, (2^k)])];
      zyg1 = BitOr[zyg1, (BitAnd[j, (2^k)])];
      zyg2 = BitOr[zyg2, (BitAnd[i, (2^k)])]]];

(*Produce a 3-dimensional matrix with the cells representing
the probability of producing a zygote genotype (k) from parental
genotypes i (mother) and j (father). Multiplying this matrix with
the mating table that gives the proportions of different male-
female genotype mating combinations will give the
frequency of zygote genotypes in the new generation
(after summing across parental genotypes).*)

RecTable = Table[0, {i, Geno}, {j, Geno}, {k, Geno}];
For[i = 0, i < Geno, i++,
  For[j = 0, j < Geno, j++,
    For[mask = 0, mask < masklim, mask++,
      MaskProb[mask, Nloci];
      zygoteProb = (1 / 2) * prob;
      ZygoteGenotypes[i, j, mask];
      RecTable[[i + 1], [j + 1], [zyg1 + 1]] += zygoteProb;
      RecTable[[i + 1], [j + 1], [zyg2 + 1]] += zygoteProb;]]]

(*uncomment this line to view the recombination table*)
(*MatrixForm[RecTable]*)

(*make a vector that will perform Natural Selection on males,
affecting gene frequencies before mating.*)

msel = Table[i, {i, 1, 8}];
u = Total[genotypes[[{1, 5}]]] + (1 - st) * Total[genotypes[[{2, 6}]]] +
  (1 - sb) * Total[genotypes[[{3, 7}]]] + (1 - sb) * (1 - st) * Total[genotypes[[{4, 8}]]];
msel[[{1, 5}]] = Table[genotypes[[i]] / u, {i, {1, 5}}];
msel[[{2, 6}]] = Table[((1 - st) * genotypes[[i]]) / u, {i, {2, 6}}];
msel[[{3, 7}]] = Table[((1 - sb) * genotypes[[i]]) / u, {i, {3, 7}}];
msel[[{4, 8}]] = Table[((1 - sb) * (1 - st) * genotypes[[i]]) / u, {i, {4, 8}}];

zb1 = (ab + 1) * Total[msel[[{1, 2, 5, 6}]]] + Total[msel[[{3, 4, 7, 8}]]];

zb2 = Total[msel[[{1, 2, 5, 6}]]] + (ab + 1) * Total[msel[[{3, 4, 7, 8}]]];

```

```

z1 = Total[mse1[{1, 5}]] * ((1 + ab) / zb1) * (c + (1 - c) * (1 / (at + 2))) +
  Total[mse1[{2, 6}]] * ((1 + ab) / zb1) * (c + (1 - c) * ((at + 1) / (at + 2))) +
  (Total[mse1[{3, 7}]] / zb1) * (c * (1 - γ) + (1 - c * (1 - γ)) * (1 / (at + 2))) +
  (Total[mse1[{4, 8}]] / zb1) * (c * (1 - γ) + (1 - c * (1 - γ)) * ((at + 1) / (at + 2)));

```

```

z2 = (Total[mse1[{1, 5}]] / zb2) * (c + (1 - c) * (1 / (at + 2))) +
  (Total[mse1[{2, 6}]] / zb2) * (c + (1 - c) * ((at + 1) / (at + 2))) +
  Total[mse1[{3, 7}]] * ((1 + ab) / zb2) * (c * (1 - γ) + (1 - c * (1 - γ)) * (1 / (at + 2))) +
  Total[mse1[{4, 8}]] * ((1 + ab) / zb2) *
  (c * (1 - γ) + (1 - c * (1 - γ)) * ((at + 1) / (at + 2)));
(*add a small cost to the bower preference, R2*)

```

```

fse1 = Table[i, {i, 1, 8}];
v = Total[genotypes[1 ;; 4]] + (1 - sr) * Total[genotypes[5 ;; 8]];
fse1[1 ;; 4] = Table[genotypes[i] / v, {i, 1, 4}];
fse1[5 ;; 8] = Table[((1 - sr) * genotypes[i]) / v, {i, 5, 8}];

```

(*mating porbability matrix-what proportion of matings will be from each pairing strictly based on genotype frequency, female choice, coercion, and bower type.*)

```
Mating = Table[Table[i, {i, 1, 8}], {j, 1, 8}];
```

(*for mating with R1 females*)

(*T1B1 males*)

```

Mating[1 ;; 4, {1, 5}] =
  Table[Table[ $\frac{fse1[j] (mse1[i] (1 + ab) (c + \frac{1-c}{at+2}))}{zb1 z1}$ , {i, {1, 5}}], {j, 1, 4}];

```

(*T2B1 males*)

```

Mating[1 ;; 4, {2, 6}] =
  Table[Table[ $\frac{fse1[j] (mse1[i] (1 + ab) (c + \frac{(1-c)(at+1)}{at+2}))}{zb1 z1}$ , {i, {2, 6}}], {j, 1, 4}];

```

(*T1B2 males*)

```

Mating[1 ;; 4, {3, 7}] =
  Table[Table[ $\frac{fse1[j] (mse1[i] (c (1 - \gamma) + \frac{1-c(1-\gamma)}{at+2}))}{zb1 z1}$ , {i, {3, 7}}], {j, 1, 4}];

```

(*T2B2 males*)

```

Mating[1 ;; 4, {4, 8}] = Table[
  Table[ $\frac{fse1[j] (mse1[i] (c (1 - \gamma) + \frac{(1-c(1-\gamma))(at+1)}{at+2}))}{zb1 z1}$ , {i, {4, 8}}], {j, 1, 4}];

```

(*for mating with R2 females*)

(*T1B1 males*)

Mating[[5 ;; 8, {1, 5}]] =

Table[Table[$\frac{f_{sel}[[j]] \left(m_{sel}[[i]] \left(c + \frac{1-c}{at+2} \right) \right)}{z_{b2} z_2}$, {i, {1, 5}}], {j, 5, 8}];

(*T2B1 males*)

Mating[[5 ;; 8, {2, 6}]] =

Table[Table[$\frac{f_{sel}[[j]] \left(m_{sel}[[i]] \left(c + \frac{(1-c)(at+1)}{at+2} \right) \right)}{z_{b2} z_2}$, {i, {2, 6}}], {j, 5, 8}];

(*T1B2 males*)

Mating[[5 ;; 8, {3, 7}]] = Table[

Table[$\frac{f_{sel}[[j]] \left(m_{sel}[[i]] (1 + ab) \left(c (1 - \gamma) + \frac{1-c(1-\gamma)}{at+2} \right) \right)}{z_{b2} z_2}$, {i, {3, 7}}], {j, 5, 8}];

(*T2B2 males*)

Mating[[5 ;; 8, {4, 8}]] = Table[Table[

$\frac{f_{sel}[[j]] \left(m_{sel}[[i]] (1 + ab) \left(c (1 - \gamma) + \frac{(1-c(1-\gamma))(at+1)}{at+2} \right) \right)}{z_{b2} z_2}$, {i, {4, 8}}], {j, 5, 8}];

(*Multiply the mating table by the recombination matrix to get the contributions to each zygote genotype weighted by the proportions of each mate pairing*)

materec = RecTable * Mating;

(*sum across each element of each 8-tuple for the mate pairings across the new matrix to get the final genotype frequencies.*)

genotypes[[1 ;; 8]] =

Table[Simplify[Total[Flatten[materec[[1 ;; 8, 1 ;; 8, i]]]], {i, 1, 8}];

(*once genotypes are assigned, some frequency from T2 alleles are shifted over to T1 alleles due to biased mutation*)

mgenotypes = {1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8};

mgenotypes[[{2, 4, 6, 8}]] = (1 - m) * genotypes[[{2, 4, 6, 8}]];

mgenotypes[[{1, 3, 5, 7}]] = m * genotypes[[{2, 4, 6, 8}]] + genotypes[[{1, 3, 5, 7}]];

T21 = Total[mgenotypes[[{2, 4, 6, 8}]]];

B21 = Total[mgenotypes[[{3, 4, 7, 8}]]];

R21 = Total[mgenotypes[[5 ;; 8]]];

DTB1 = Total[mgenotypes[[{4, 8}]]] - T21 * B21;

DTR1 = Total[mgenotypes[[{6, 8}]]] - T21 * R21;

```
DBR1 = Total[mgenotypes[[{7, 8}]]] - B21 * R21;
DTBR1 = mgenotypes[[8]] - T21 * DBR1 - B21 * DTR1 - R21 * DTB1 - T21 * B21 * R21;
```

(*We are interested in evolution by indirect selection,
so we have to look ahead to the second
generation to see if R2 and B2 will increase*)

(*for the first generation, the D's start at zero,
so the new value will just be the magnitude of the ΔD .*)

(*first, get the recursion equations and solve for the first generation
Beware- this code cell is computationally intensive and may
take a very long time to run (about an hour on an intel i7 iMac)*)

```
 $\Delta T2 = \text{Simplify}[T21 - T2];$ 
 $\Delta B2 = \text{Simplify}[B21 - B2];$ 
 $\Delta R2 = \text{Simplify}[R21 - R2];$ 
 $\Delta DBR = \text{Simplify}[DBR1 - DBR];$ 
 $\Delta DTB = \text{Simplify}[DTB1 - DTB];$ 
 $\Delta DTR = \text{Simplify}[DTR1 - DTR];$ 
 $\Delta DTBR = \text{Simplify}[DTBR1 - DTBR];$ 
```

```
In[ ]:= Tdelt1 =
```

```
Simplify[ $\Delta T2 /. \{T2 \rightarrow T_{eq}, R2 \rightarrow 1/2, B2 \rightarrow 1/2, DBR \rightarrow 0, DTB \rightarrow 0, DTR \rightarrow 0, DTBR \rightarrow 0\}$ ]
```

```
Out[ ]:= - ( ( at (2 + at) c (29 (1 + c) + at (-81 + 110 c))
   $\gamma$  (9 ab2 ((1 + c)2 + at2 (-9 + 10 c) + 2 at (-4 + c + 5 c2)) +
    2 (-9 (1 + c) (-2 + c (-2 +  $\gamma$ )) + 2 at2 (-81 + 10 c (9 +  $\gamma$ )) +
      at (-144 - 90 c2 (-2 +  $\gamma$ ) + c (36 + 121  $\gamma$ ))) + 2 ab (-9 (1 + c) (-2 + c (-2 +  $\gamma$ )) +
        2 at2 (-81 + 10 c (9 +  $\gamma$ )) + at (-144 - 90 c2 (-2 +  $\gamma$ ) + c (36 + 121  $\gamma$ ))) ) ) /
  (2 (1 + c + at (-9 + 10 c)) (9 ab ((1 + c)2 + at2 (-9 + 10 c) + 2 at (-4 + c + 5 c2)) -
    9 (1 + c) (-2 + c (-2 +  $\gamma$ )) + 2 at2 (-81 + 10 c (9 +  $\gamma$ )) +
    at (-144 - 90 c2 (-2 +  $\gamma$ ) + c (36 + 121  $\gamma$ )))
  (-9 (1 + c) (-2 + c (-2 +  $\gamma$ )) + 2 at2 (-81 + 10 c (9 +  $\gamma$ )) +
    at (-144 - 90 c2 (-2 +  $\gamma$ ) + c (36 + 121  $\gamma$ ))) + ab (-9 (1 + c) (-1 + c (-1 +  $\gamma$ )) +
    at2 (-81 + 10 c (9 + 2  $\gamma$ )) + at (-72 - 90 c2 (-1 +  $\gamma$ ) + c (18 + 121  $\gamma$ ))) ) ) )
```

In[*]:= **T2plus = Simplify[Teq + Tdelt1]**

$$\text{Out[*]} = \frac{1}{22 (1 + c + at (-9 + 10 c))} (29 (1 + c) + at (-81 + 110 c)) \\ (2 - (11 at (2 + at) c \gamma (9 ab^2 ((1 + c)^2 + at^2 (-9 + 10 c) + 2 at (-4 + c + 5 c^2)) + \\ 2 (-9 (1 + c) (-2 + c (-2 + \gamma)) + 2 at^2 (-81 + 10 c (9 + \gamma)) + at \\ (-144 - 90 c^2 (-2 + \gamma) + c (36 + 121 \gamma))) + 2 ab (-9 (1 + c) (-2 + c (-2 + \gamma)) + \\ 2 at^2 (-81 + 10 c (9 + \gamma)) + at (-144 - 90 c^2 (-2 + \gamma) + c (36 + 121 \gamma)))) / \\ ((9 ab ((1 + c)^2 + at^2 (-9 + 10 c) + 2 at (-4 + c + 5 c^2)) - 9 (1 + c) (-2 + c (-2 + \gamma)) + \\ 2 at^2 (-81 + 10 c (9 + \gamma)) + at (-144 - 90 c^2 (-2 + \gamma) + c (36 + 121 \gamma))) \\ (-9 (1 + c) (-2 + c (-2 + \gamma)) + 2 at^2 (-81 + 10 c (9 + \gamma)) + \\ at (-144 - 90 c^2 (-2 + \gamma) + c (36 + 121 \gamma)) + ab (-9 (1 + c) (-1 + c (-1 + \gamma)) + \\ at^2 (-81 + 10 c (9 + 2 \gamma)) + at (-72 - 90 c^2 (-1 + \gamma) + c (18 + 121 \gamma))))))$$

In[*]:= **Bdelt1 =**

Simplify[ΔB2 /. {T2 → Teq, R2 → 1 / 2, B2 → 1 / 2, DBR → 0, DTB → 0, DTR → 0, DTBR → 0}]

$$\text{Out[*]} = ((1 + ab) c (9 - 121 at - 20 at^2 + 9 c + 90 at c) \gamma (9 (1 + c) (-2 + c (-2 + \gamma)) - \\ 2 at^2 (-81 + 10 c (9 + \gamma)) + at (144 + 90 c^2 (-2 + \gamma) - c (36 + 121 \gamma)))) / \\ (4 (9 ab ((1 + c)^2 + at^2 (-9 + 10 c) + 2 at (-4 + c + 5 c^2)) - 9 (1 + c) (-2 + c (-2 + \gamma)) + \\ 2 at^2 (-81 + 10 c (9 + \gamma)) + at (-144 - 90 c^2 (-2 + \gamma) + c (36 + 121 \gamma))) \\ (-9 (1 + c) (-2 + c (-2 + \gamma)) + 2 at^2 (-81 + 10 c (9 + \gamma)) + \\ at (-144 - 90 c^2 (-2 + \gamma) + c (36 + 121 \gamma)) + ab (-9 (1 + c) (-1 + c (-1 + \gamma)) + \\ at^2 (-81 + 10 c (9 + 2 \gamma)) + at (-72 - 90 c^2 (-1 + \gamma) + c (18 + 121 \gamma))))$$

In[*]:= **B2plus = Bdelt1 + 1 / 2;**

In[*]:= **Rdelt1 =**

Simplify[ΔR2 /. {T2 → Teq, R2 → 1 / 2, B2 → 1 / 2, DBR → 0, DTB → 0, DTR → 0, DTBR → 0}]

Out[*]= 0

In[*]:= **R2plus = Rdelt1 + 1 / 2;**

In[*]:= **DBRplus =**

Simplify[ΔDBR /. {T2 → Teq, R2 → 1 / 2, B2 → 1 / 2, DBR → 0, DTB → 0, DTR → 0, DTBR → 0}]

$$\text{Out[*]} = (9 ab (2 + ab) ((1 + c)^2 + at^2 (-9 + 10 c) + 2 at (-4 + c + 5 c^2)) (-9 (1 + c) (-1 + c (-1 + \gamma)) + \\ at^2 (-81 + 10 c (9 + 2 \gamma)) + at (-72 - 90 c^2 (-1 + \gamma) + c (18 + 121 \gamma)))) / \\ (16 (9 ab ((1 + c)^2 + at^2 (-9 + 10 c) + 2 at (-4 + c + 5 c^2)) - 9 (1 + c) (-2 + c (-2 + \gamma)) + \\ 2 at^2 (-81 + 10 c (9 + \gamma)) + at (-144 - 90 c^2 (-2 + \gamma) + c (36 + 121 \gamma))) \\ (-9 (1 + c) (-2 + c (-2 + \gamma)) + 2 at^2 (-81 + 10 c (9 + \gamma)) + \\ at (-144 - 90 c^2 (-2 + \gamma) + c (36 + 121 \gamma)) + ab (-9 (1 + c) (-1 + c (-1 + \gamma)) + \\ at^2 (-81 + 10 c (9 + 2 \gamma)) + at (-72 - 90 c^2 (-1 + \gamma) + c (18 + 121 \gamma))))$$

In[*]:= DTBplus =

Simplify[ΔDTB /. {T2 → Teq, R2 → 1 / 2, B2 → 1 / 2, DBR → 0, DTB → 0, DTR → 0, DTBR → 0}]

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Out[*]} = & - \left(\left(9 \text{ at } (2 + \text{ at}) \text{ c } (1 + \text{ at} + \text{ c}) (29 (1 + \text{ c}) + \text{ at } (-81 + 110 \text{ c})) \gamma \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left(9 \text{ ab}^4 \left((1 + \text{ c})^2 + \text{ at}^2 (-9 + 10 \text{ c}) + 2 \text{ at } (-4 + \text{ c} + 5 \text{ c}^2) \right) (-9 (1 + \text{ c}) (-1 + \text{ c} (-1 + \gamma)) + \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. \text{ at}^2 (-81 + 10 \text{ c} (9 + 2 \gamma)) + \text{ at } (-72 - 90 \text{ c}^2 (-1 + \gamma) + \text{ c } (18 + 121 \gamma)) \right) \right) + \\ & 4 (-9 (1 + \text{ c}) (-2 + \text{ c} (-2 + \gamma)) + 2 \text{ at}^2 (-81 + 10 \text{ c} (9 + \gamma)) + \\ & \left. \text{ at } (-144 - 90 \text{ c}^2 (-2 + \gamma) + \text{ c } (36 + 121 \gamma)) \right)^2 + \\ & 8 \text{ ab } (-9 (1 + \text{ c}) (-2 + \text{ c} (-2 + \gamma)) + 2 \text{ at}^2 (-81 + 10 \text{ c} (9 + \gamma)) + \\ & \left. \text{ at } (-144 - 90 \text{ c}^2 (-2 + \gamma) + \text{ c } (36 + 121 \gamma)) \right)^2 + \\ & 6 \text{ ab}^2 (-9 (1 + \text{ c}) (-2 + \text{ c} (-2 + \gamma)) + 2 \text{ at}^2 (-81 + 10 \text{ c} (9 + \gamma)) + \\ & \left. \text{ at } (-144 - 90 \text{ c}^2 (-2 + \gamma) + \text{ c } (36 + 121 \gamma)) \right)^2 + \\ & 2 \text{ ab}^3 (-9 (1 + \text{ c}) (-2 + \text{ c} (-2 + \gamma)) + 2 \text{ at}^2 (-81 + 10 \text{ c} (9 + \gamma)) + \\ & \left. \text{ at } (-144 - 90 \text{ c}^2 (-2 + \gamma) + \text{ c } (36 + 121 \gamma)) \right)^2 \Big) / \\ & \left(8 (9 \text{ ab } \left((1 + \text{ c})^2 + \text{ at}^2 (-9 + 10 \text{ c}) + 2 \text{ at } (-4 + \text{ c} + 5 \text{ c}^2) \right) - 9 (1 + \text{ c}) (-2 + \text{ c} (-2 + \gamma)) + \right. \\ & \left. 2 \text{ at}^2 (-81 + 10 \text{ c} (9 + \gamma)) + \text{ at } (-144 - 90 \text{ c}^2 (-2 + \gamma) + \text{ c } (36 + 121 \gamma)) \right)^2 \\ & (-9 (1 + \text{ c}) (-2 + \text{ c} (-2 + \gamma)) + 2 \text{ at}^2 (-81 + 10 \text{ c} (9 + \gamma)) + \\ & \left. \text{ at } (-144 - 90 \text{ c}^2 (-2 + \gamma) + \text{ c } (36 + 121 \gamma)) + \text{ ab } (-9 (1 + \text{ c}) (-1 + \text{ c} (-1 + \gamma)) + \right. \\ & \left. \left. \text{ at}^2 (-81 + 10 \text{ c} (9 + 2 \gamma)) + \text{ at } (-72 - 90 \text{ c}^2 (-1 + \gamma) + \text{ c } (18 + 121 \gamma)) \right) \right)^2 \Big) \end{aligned}$$

In[*]:= DTRplus =

Simplify[ΔDTR /. {T2 → Teq, R2 → 1 / 2, B2 → 1 / 2, DBR → 0, DTB → 0, DTR → 0, DTBR → 0}]

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Out[*]} = & - \left((9 \text{ ab } (2 + \text{ ab}) \text{ at } (2 + \text{ at}) \text{ c } (1 + \text{ at} + \text{ c}) (29 (1 + \text{ c}) + \text{ at } (-81 + 110 \text{ c})) \gamma) / \right. \\ & \left(9 \text{ ab } \left((1 + \text{ c})^2 + \text{ at}^2 (-9 + 10 \text{ c}) + 2 \text{ at } (-4 + \text{ c} + 5 \text{ c}^2) \right) - 9 (1 + \text{ c}) (-2 + \text{ c} (-2 + \gamma)) + \right. \\ & \left. 2 \text{ at}^2 (-81 + 10 \text{ c} (9 + \gamma)) + \text{ at } (-144 - 90 \text{ c}^2 (-2 + \gamma) + \text{ c } (36 + 121 \gamma)) \right) \\ & (-9 (1 + \text{ c}) (-2 + \text{ c} (-2 + \gamma)) + 2 \text{ at}^2 (-81 + 10 \text{ c} (9 + \gamma)) + \\ & \left. \text{ at } (-144 - 90 \text{ c}^2 (-2 + \gamma) + \text{ c } (36 + 121 \gamma)) + \text{ ab } (-9 (1 + \text{ c}) (-1 + \text{ c} (-1 + \gamma)) + \right. \\ & \left. \left. \text{ at}^2 (-81 + 10 \text{ c} (9 + 2 \gamma)) + \text{ at } (-72 - 90 \text{ c}^2 (-1 + \gamma) + \text{ c } (18 + 121 \gamma)) \right) \right) \Big) \end{aligned}$$

In[*]:= DTBRplus = Simplify[

ΔDTBR /. {T2 → Teq, R2 → 1 / 2, B2 → 1 / 2, DBR → 0, DTB → 0, DTR → 0, DTBR → 0}]

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Out[*]} = & (9 \text{ ab } (2 + 3 \text{ ab} + \text{ ab}^2) \text{ at } (2 + \text{ at}) \text{ c}^2 (29 (1 + \text{ c}) + \text{ at } (-81 + 110 \text{ c})) \\ & (20 \text{ at}^3 + \text{ at}^2 (141 - 70 \text{ c}) - 9 (1 + \text{ c})^2 + \text{ at } (112 + 22 \text{ c} - 90 \text{ c}^2)) \\ & \gamma^2 (-9 (1 + \text{ c}) (-2 + \text{ c} (-2 + \gamma)) + 2 \text{ at}^2 (-81 + 10 \text{ c} (9 + \gamma)) + \\ & \left. \text{ at } (-144 - 90 \text{ c}^2 (-2 + \gamma) + \text{ c } (36 + 121 \gamma)) \right) \Big) / \\ & \left(16 (9 \text{ ab } \left((1 + \text{ c})^2 + \text{ at}^2 (-9 + 10 \text{ c}) + 2 \text{ at } (-4 + \text{ c} + 5 \text{ c}^2) \right) - 9 (1 + \text{ c}) (-2 + \text{ c} (-2 + \gamma)) + \right. \\ & \left. 2 \text{ at}^2 (-81 + 10 \text{ c} (9 + \gamma)) + \text{ at } (-144 - 90 \text{ c}^2 (-2 + \gamma) + \text{ c } (36 + 121 \gamma)) \right)^2 \\ & (-9 (1 + \text{ c}) (-2 + \text{ c} (-2 + \gamma)) + 2 \text{ at}^2 (-81 + 10 \text{ c} (9 + \gamma)) + \\ & \left. \text{ at } (-144 - 90 \text{ c}^2 (-2 + \gamma) + \text{ c } (36 + 121 \gamma)) + \text{ ab } (-9 (1 + \text{ c}) (-1 + \text{ c} (-1 + \gamma)) + \right. \\ & \left. \left. \text{ at}^2 (-81 + 10 \text{ c} (9 + 2 \gamma)) + \text{ at } (-72 - 90 \text{ c}^2 (-1 + \gamma) + \text{ c } (18 + 121 \gamma)) \right) \right)^2 \end{aligned}$$

(*now figure out the ΔR for the next generation.*)

```
In[*]:= Rdelt2 = Simplify[ΔR2 /. {T2 → T2plus, R2 → R2plus, B2 → B2plus,
    DBR → DBRplus, DTB → DTBplus, DTR → DTRplus, DTBR → DTBRplus}];
```

```
In[158]:= (*The cell below is the same expression for Rdelt2 as a function of c,
    at, ab, and γ. Need to have it written out or MMA won'
    t define the function properly. Expand cell to view.*)
```

```
(*Explore Graphically;
```

```
R2 is favored in this scenario as long as ab is strong enough*)
```

```
In[*]:= Manipulate[Plot[Rdelt2func[c, at, ab, γ], {γ, 0, 1}, PlotRange → Full],
    {c, 0,  $\frac{at - 2m - atm + (1 + at)(-1 + m)st}{at + 2m + atm + st - mst}$ },
    {{at, 4}, -1 +  $\frac{1 + m}{(-1 + m)(-1 + st)}$ , 16}, {ab, 0, 20}]
```



```

In[ ]:= fig4nofill = Plot[{Rdelt2func[0.45, 5, 16,  $\gamma$ ], Rdelt2func[0.45, 5, 12,  $\gamma$ ],
  Rdelt2func[0.45, 5, 8,  $\gamma$ ], Rdelt2func[0.45, 5, 4,  $\gamma$ ]},
  { $\gamma$ , 0, 1}, PlotStyle -> {{ColorData["GrayTones", 8.5 / 10]},
  {ColorData["GrayTones", 6.5 / 10]}, {ColorData["GrayTones", 3.5 / 10]},
  {ColorData["GrayTones", 0 / 10]}}, Frame -> True, FrameStyle ->
  {{{18, Black, FontFamily -> "Times"}}, {18, Black, FontFamily -> "Times"}},
  {{18, Black, FontFamily -> "Times"}, {18, Black, FontFamily -> "Times"}},
  FrameLabel -> {Text[Style["Effectiveness of protection,  $\gamma$ ",
  FontFamily -> "Times", FontSize -> 22]],
  Rotate[Text[Style[Row[{" $\Delta$ ", Subscript["R", "2"]}], FontFamily -> "Times",
  FontSize -> 22]], - $\pi$  / 2]}, ImageSize -> 576, PlotLegends ->
  Placed[LineLegend[{{Row[{Style[Subscript["a", "b"], Italic], "=16" }]},
  Row[{Style[Subscript["a", "b"], Italic], "=12" }]},
  Row[{Style[Subscript["a", "b"], Italic], "=8" }]},
  Row[{Style[Subscript["a", "b"], Italic], "=4" }]}]},
  LabelStyle -> {18, FontFamily -> "Times"}, LegendLayout -> "Column",
  {0.15, 0.7}], ImagePadding -> {{120, 30}, {60, 30}}]

```

